

MENTAL HEALTH IN RELATION TO SELF-EFFICACY OF SIGHTED AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study analyzed associations of general self-efficacy and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students in which 40 students with visual impairment and 40 students without visual impairment of Haryana and Chandigarh blind and public schools . There was positive relationship between total self –efficacy and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students. The findings show that there is positive relationship between self-efficacy and mental health. It means efforts to improve self efficacy will also contribute to the improvement in mental health of students.

Keywords: *'self-efficacy, mental health, visual impairment, sighted,*

Introduction:

The eye is very important sensory organ, which accounts for a very large fraction of the total information's available to a person through his sense. Thus, lack of sight makes the individual aloof from the physical world. This sensory, social and physical isolation creates anxiety and adjustment problems in the personality of Blind persons in the society.

Individual with all sense organs intact also have to face lot of problems of adjustment which becomes hurdles' in the achievement of their goals. This further creates shades of anxiety in them. The condition of individual becomes more deplorable and serious when he/she suffers from visual impairment. Since, visually impaired children also have to live in society; it may affect their psychological processes. The visually impaired people want to be treated like any other individual. Most visually impaired people do not seek pity or even unnecessary help though they may be need assistance in some situations. Though, they appreciate the sensitivity of others but they want to be reminded of their similarities rather than their differences. The Visually impaired person has a variety of symbols- white cane, darkened glass and a sighted guide etc.

As we emphasize on Education for All , the children with special needs are great concern. Blindness is a medical phenomenon which relates to impaired sense of vision. The psychological development of a blind child is not affected due to blindness as it is disrupted by emotional overtones of blindness, for the parents and community. It is now a well known fact from research that children tend to achieve or the significant persons in their environment

expect them to achieve. But once the community does not treat them as individuals, they are lost into crowd, the crowd of blind persons. Once, the parents' stops treating the child as a developing individual, once they refuse to accept his/her capabilities and limitations, both, in a realistic manner, his self concept is bond to be severely affected. Over protection robs him of his independence, neglect turns him to undesirable behaviour. In the words of Lowenfield, blindness imposes three basic limitations on the individual: in the range and variety of experience; in the ability to get about and in the control of the environment and self in relation to it.

Mental health is an integral component of total health so mental health is not merely an absence of mental illness. It is a balance between all aspects of life like, emotional, economical, spiritual as well as physical which shows how we feel and think about self, others and how we face life's situations.

Metal health problems affect the people of all age group. The health problems occur due to psycho-social problems among all individuals. The sighted and visually impaired people both have same affect of mental health on their personality. Self –efficacy beliefs determine how people feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Such belief produces these diverse effects through four major processes. These include cognitive, motivational, affective and selection process. It has been suggested that self-efficacy is a primary factor in adjustment to visual impairment (Dodds, 1989). Acquiring realistic expectations about one's competencies is one of the most important aspects of adjustment to visual impairment. Because origins of self-efficacy lie in the appraisal of past performances (Bandura, 1982, 1997), past self-efficacy beliefs may no longer be realistic when visual abilities decline. In contrast, people who doubt their capacities shy away from difficult tasks which they view as personal threats. They have low aspirations and weak commitment to goals they choose to pursue.

The blind children have a feeling of insecurity because of their various psychological and physical factors including causalities such as blindness. It is further seen that relationship between mental health and self- efficacy has also impact the growth and development of individuals.

It is shows by research that sighted and visually impaired students differs significantly in terms of their mental health and self –efficacy level. Whereas some studies have assessed self-efficacy beliefs in older adults with visual impairment (Brown & Barrett, 2011; Ormel, Kempen, Penninx, Brilman, Beekman, & VanSonderen, 1997; Talbert-Kipasa, 2008), there is a surprising lack of research on this topic in children and adolescents with visual impairment.

Keeping these facts in mind the present study is a effort to investigate mental health in relation to self-efficacy of sighted and visually impaired students.

Method

In the present research purposive sample of 40 visually impaired students and 40 sighted students at secondary level selected from Haryana and Chandigarh.

Tools used: mental health inventory developed by Jagdish and Shri Vastav and self –efficacy questionnaire developed by Muris.

Design:

Sr no.	Name of school	No. of students	State
1	Institute for the Blind , Chandigarh	22	Chandigarh
2	Govt. school for Blind , Panipat	18	Haryana
3	DAV Sen Sec. School , Kurukshetra	17	Haryana
4	Maharaja Partap Sen. Sec .School, kurukshetra	23	Haryana

Techniques:

After collection of the data, the same was put into a tabular form to make the process of analysis easier. The product moment method of correlation in order to find out the relationship between mental health and self-efficacy was used also to examine the difference between relent groups t-test was used.

Results:

Pearson’s co-efficient of correlation method is used to see the relationship between mental health and self –efficacy in table 1 perceived by 80 students.

Table 1 . Coefficient of correlation for mental health and self –efficacy

Sr. no.	Variables	r	Level of Significance at 0.05
1	Set/mht	0.34	Significant
2	Set/mh1	0.23	Significant
3	Set/mh2	0.31	Significant
4	Set/mh3	0.42	Significant
5	Set/mh4	0.29	Significant
6	Set/mh5	0.25	Significant

The value of r for self- efficacy and total mental health is 0.34 which is significant at 0.05 levels. Also the value of r is 0.23 for self efficacy and self evaluation which exceed the critical value (.204) at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is significant level. The obtain value of r is 0.31 for self efficacy and perception of reality which is significant at 0.05 level. Similarly, the r value is 0.42 of self efficacy and personality which is significant so there is positive relationship between integration of personality and self –efficacy. The obtain value of r for slf efficacy and aoutonomy is 0.29 which is significant. The value of r for self efficacy and group orientated attitude is 0.25 which is also significant.

Findings:

- ❖ There was positive relationship between total self –efficacy and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.
- ❖ There was positive relationship between social self- efficacy and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.
- ❖ There was positive relationship between emotional self efficacy and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.
- ❖ There was significant difference between total mental health of visually impaired and sighted students. Sighted students found better than visually impaired in terms of mental health.
- ❖ There was significant difference between academic self efficacy among visually impaired and sighted students. Sighed students found better in terms of visually impaired students.
- ❖ There was significant difference between social self –efficacy of sighted and visually impaired students.

Educational implications:

Its implications for teachers, administrators and parents of sighted and visually impaired students. Self -efficacy and mental health are two important factors in the development of individual. It is the most important duty of teachers and parents to develop excellent mental health in visually impaired and sighted student during their educational period at school level. The findings show that there is positive relationship between self-efficacy and mental health. It means efforts to improve self efficacy will also contribute to the improvement in mental health of students. Therefore administrator, school teachers and parents should make special efforts to improve self –efficacy and mental health of such students by providing them more congenial environment and opportunity of social interaction.

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